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Predicting Cognitive Profiles from a Mini Quiz: A Facebook Game for Cultural Heritage

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Abstract

Games are used in cultural heritage to engage visitors, to function as learning tools, or even advertise a venue. However, games can be also used for quick profiling purposes to overcome the cold start problem of personalized museum applications. A profiling game aiming to extract users' cognitive profiles was developed and tested with real users. The game follows the principles of pop psychology quizzes. The results of the game showed its potential in correctly predicting the cognitive profiles of users with average success rate around 90%. Being an entertaining and engaging way to involve visitors with diverse needs, games and especially profiling have a clear place in cultural heritage and should be investigated further. Our future work will focus on games that will try to predict different personality aspects, like Big Five dimensions.
